

RELATIONAL ANALYSIS OF FLORICULTURE GROWERS WITH THEIR ENTREPRENEURIAL BEHAVIOUR

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ABSTRACT

The present study was carried out during year 2022-23 to know the 'entrepreneurial behaviour of floriculture growers' and 'relationship between personal, socio-economic characteristics of floriculture growers and their entrepreneurial behaviour'. Ex-post-facto research design was used for the present study. Data were collected with the help of pre-structured interview schedule. The collected data was analyzed by using statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentage and correlation. The data revealed that 65.83 per cent of the respondents belonged to medium entrepreneurial behavior. Whereas, 17.50 per cent and 16.67 per cent had low and high level of entrepreneurial behavior respectively. Independent variables namely, education, size of land holding, area under polyhouse, annual income, credibility, risk orientation, planning orientation, marketing behavior and place of market were positive and highly significant relationship with the entrepreneurial behavior of floriculture growers while age was negative and non-significant relationship with the entrepreneurial behaviour of floriculture growers.

Majority of the floriculture growers had medium entrepreneurial behaviour. It is clear indication of the farmer's progressiveness. Therefore, it calls for intensification of educational efforts and policy support to the protected cultivation by the field extension workers of the development departments, NGO's and private organizations. As majority of the respondents had medium innovativeness, still there is a need to expose the farmers to new developments in agriculture technologies and motivate them to adopt the new technologies by organizing group discussions, meetings and field trips.

The study revealed that certain variable such as education, land holding, annual income, credibility, planning orientation, risk orientation, marketing behaviour found significant relationship with entrepreneurial behaviour. The government and private organizations should aim at manipulating these variables to their advantage for promoting entrepreneurs in floriculture.

(Key words: Floriculture growers, entrepreneurial behaviour, relationship, independent variables, significant)

INTRODUCTION

In today's changing scenario, skills in entrepreneurial development have become more important. Many entrepreneurial opportunities are emerging in various fields such as computers, electronics, medicine, agriculture, food technology, fashion designing etc. Entrepreneurship is the central force of economic activity and prime mover of development and most needed component for the development. The findings of the study may help the administrators and policy makers to know the entrepreneurial behaviour of farmers. Entrepreneurial behaviour refers to the way entrepreneurs act and think. Maharashtra is one of

the leading flower producers in the country after Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh. The state has varying soil types and agroclimatic conditions, which offers tremendous scope for commercial floriculture. The districts like Pune, Nasik, Ahmednagar, Sangli, Kolhapur, Thane, Nagpur, Satara are well known for flower cultivation. Pune district is supposed to be a district of "corporate high-tech floriculture". Small farmers of Kolhapur and Sangli districts are hi-tech floriculture and Nasik and Ahmednagar for open flowers cultivation. The principal flowers grown in Maharashtra are roses, carnation, chrysanthemum, marigold, aster, jasmine etc. In polyhouses, the important flowers grown are roses, carnation, orchid, tulip, gerbera etc. The climate of Deccan

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plateau is most suitable for growing roses, carnation, gerbera, chrysanthemum, mogra, tuberose etc., while coastal climate is suitable for orchid and Anthurium. The protected cultivation of flowers and other high value of plants on a commercial scale in big polyhouses came into existence. However, such cultivation was limited to the corporate entities and the rich amongst the farming community as it involved very high financial outlay and technical support. The high financial outlay was mainly due to import of technology and equipments. Over the years this technology has been indigenized to suit local conditions. This has resulted in emergence of low cost polyhouses, with the advent of which even the small and marginal farmers are now able to exploit the benefits of protected cultivation. Government of Maharashtra is promoting floriculture in the state by giving assistance to this sector. The National Horticulture Board is also promoting floriculture sector by giving back ended assistance @ 20 % of the project cost. Marigold (*Tagetes erecta*) is one of the most commonly grown commercial flower crop in India. Marigold is extensively cultivated for its great demand as loose flower, also used as potted plant as well as bedding plant. It is cultivated commercially in most parts of India for pigment extraction. (Mahanta *et al.*, 2020).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present study was conducted during year 2022-23 in Sangli and Kolhapur district of Maharashtra state. Palus, Kadegaon, Miraj talukas from Sangli and Shirol, Karvir, Hatkanangle talukas from Kolhapur district were selected. With the help of Department of Horticulture, Department of Agriculture and private organizations working in the field of horticulture detailed information of floriculturists from Sangli and Kolhapur was collected. From each taluka total 20 respondents were selected. Thus, total 120 respondents were selected for the present study. Ex-post-facto research design was used for the present study. Entrepreneurial behaviour is a broad term and it includes different parameters. 77 Entrepreneurial behaviour items were grouped under different heads namely innovativeness (9), achievement motivation (11), economic motivation (6), decision making ability (40), leadership ability (5) and management orientation (6). The Entrepreneurial behaviour, score of each item was obtained on two point continuums namely agree and disagree with weightage 1 and 0, respectively. The total score of each item was calculated by summing up of the score of all the respondents on the basis of score obtained. An interview schedule was prepared in *Marathi* language based on the objectives of the study for data collection. The data was collected with the help of pre tested interview schedule by personal interview method. Statistical tools such as mean, standard deviation, frequency, percentage and correlation was used for the analysis of data.

Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) was used to find out zero order correlation between dependent and independent variables to see the nature of relationship existed.

$$r = \frac{N\Sigma XY - \Sigma X\Sigma Y}{\sqrt{[N\Sigma X^2 - (\Sigma X)^2][N\Sigma Y^2 - (\Sigma Y)^2]}}$$

Where,

N = Number of respondents

ΣXY = Sum of products of dependent and independent variables

ΣX = Sum of independent variables

ΣX^2 = Sum of square of independent variables

ΣY = Sum of dependent variable

ΣY^2 = Sum of square of dependent variable

$(\Sigma X)^2$ = Square of sum of independent variables

$(\Sigma Y)^2$ = Square of sum of dependent variable

r = Correlation coefficient

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Entrepreneurial behaviour of floriculture growers

This indicates the outlook and perspective of the entrepreneur with reference to various entrepreneurial aspects of floriculture business. The entrepreneurial behaviour of floriculture growers were analyzed by using collected information from the respondents. They were grouped into three categories by using mean SD and result was presented in Table 1 and graphical representation given in Figure 1.

It is evident from the Table 1 that 65.83 per cent of the respondents belonged to medium entrepreneurial behaviour. Whereas, 17.50 per cent and 16.67 per cent had low and high level of entrepreneurial behaviour, respectively. The possible reasons might be due to their level of innovativeness, achievement motivation, risk taking ability, leadership ability, economic motivation, decision-making ability and management orientation.

The results are in conformity with the findings of Gaikwad and Lalhriatpuii (2018). They reported that majority of the respondents (65.00%) had medium level of entrepreneurial behaviour, whereas Malivad (2016) and Thakare (2013) reported that 15.00 per cent and 20.00 per cent of the respondents had high and low level of entrepreneurial behaviour, respectively.

Relationship between personal, socio-economic characteristics and entrepreneurial behaviour of floriculture growers

In correlation analysis, it is revealed from Table 2 that, independent variables namely, education, size of land holding, area under polyhouse, annual income, credibility, risk orientation, planning orientation, marketing behaviour and place of market were positive and highly significant relationship with the entrepreneurial behaviour of floriculture growers while age had negative and non-significant relationship with the entrepreneurial behavior of floriculture growers. The result is given in Table 2 and empirical model showing the relationship was represented in Figure 2.

Table 1. Distribution of respondents according to their entrepreneurial behaviour

Sr. No.	Category	Respondents (N=120)	
		Frequency	Percentage
1.	Low (up to 49.00)	21	17.50
2.	Medium (50.00 to 73.00)	79	65.83
3.	High (74.00 and above)	20	16.67
	Total	120	100.00

Figure 1. Entrepreneurial behaviour of floriculture growers

Table 2. Relationship between personal, socio-economic characteristic of floriculture growers and entrepreneurial behaviour

Sr. No.	Independent variables	Correlation coefficient (r)
1.	Age	-0.097 ^{NS}
2.	Education	0.259**
3.	Size of land holding	0.394**
4.	Area under Polyhouse	0.267**
5.	Annual income	0.284**
6.	Credibility	0.321**
7.	Risk orientation	0.373**
8.	Planning orientation	0.406**
9.	Marketing behaviour	0.475**
10.	Place of market	0.457**

* Significant at 0.5 per cent ** Highly significant at 1 per cent, NS = Non-significant

Figure 2. Empirical model showing the relationship between personal, socio-economic characteristics of floriculture growers and entrepreneurial behavior

1. Age and entrepreneurial behaviour

It is observed from Table 2 that, there was negative and non-significant (-0.097) relationship between age of the floriculture growers and their entrepreneurial behaviour. As age increased the entrepreneurial behaviour showed negative relationship. The results are in conformity with the findings of Gaikwad and Lalhriatpuii (2018). They have reported that on an average the entrepreneurs in other agri-businesses are either in the middle or old age category.

2. Education and entrepreneurial behaviour

It is observed from Table 2 that, there was positive and highly significant (0.259) relationship between education of the floriculture growers and their entrepreneurial behaviour. Education helps the respondents to get information from various sources. It seems to inter related with the respondents to bring changes in their socio-economic orientation to adopt new ideas, practices and motivated for taking risk. It also helps in better management over planning, production and marketing.

3. Size of land holding and entrepreneurial behaviour

It is observed from Table 2 that, there was positive and highly significant (0.394) relationship between size of land holding of the floriculture growers and their entrepreneurial behaviour. It helps to bear risk and respondents with large size of land holding had high leadership ability.

The results are in conformity with the findings of Kulkarni and Jahagirdar (2019). They reported that, the characteristics such as education, annual income, mass media exposure and extension contact had positive and significant relationship with entrepreneurial behaviour at 1% and scientific orientation and family size were positive and significant relationship with entrepreneurial behaviour.

4. Area under polyhouse and entrepreneurial behaviour

It is observed from Table 2 that, there was positive and highly significant (0.267) relationship between area under polyhouse of the floriculture growers and their entrepreneurial behavior. It acts as economic base for efficient decision making to apply new ideas for achieving maximum profits.

5. Annual income and entrepreneurial behaviour

It is observed from Table 2 that, there was positive and highly significant (0.284) relationship between annual income of the floriculture growers and their entrepreneurial behaviour. Respondents with more annual income had higher purchasing power and urge to invest in specialized farm operations. It helped them to bear risk against uncertainty and motivated for adoption of innovations.

6. Credibility and entrepreneurial behaviour

It is observed from Table 2 that, there was positive and highly significant (0.321) relationship between credibility of the floriculture growers and their

entrepreneurial behaviour. Respondents with more credibility had higher purchasing power and urge to invest in specialized farm operations. It helps them to bear risk against uncertainty and motivated for adoption of innovation.

7. Risk orientation and entrepreneurial behaviour

It is observed from Table 2 that, there was positive and highly significant (0.373) relationship between risk orientation of the floriculture growers and their entrepreneurial behaviour. It helped to develop leadership ability among the respondents of the society and motivated for socio-economic growth and achievement. The results are in conformity with the findings of Bhaskar *et al.* (2019), they reported that nearly three-fourth (74.17%) of the nursery owners had medium level of risk orientation.

8. Planning orientation and entrepreneurial behaviour

It is observed from Table 2 that, there was positive and highly significant (0.406) relationship between planning orientation of the floriculture growers and their entrepreneurial behavior.

9. Marketing behaviour and entrepreneurial behaviour

It is observed from Table 2 that, there was positive and highly significant (0.475) relationship between marketing behaviour of the floriculture growers and their entrepreneurial behaviour. Create favourable attitude towards risk taking ability.

10. Place of market and entrepreneurial behaviour

It is observed from Table 2 that, there was positive and highly significant (0.457) relationship between place of market of the floriculture growers and their entrepreneurial behaviour. The results are in conformity with the findings of Gaikwad and Lalhriatpuii (2018). Majority of the floriculture growers had medium entrepreneurial behavior. It is clear indication of the farmer's progressiveness. Therefore, it calls for intensification of educational efforts and policy support to the protected cultivation by the field extension workers of the development departments, NGO's and private organizations. As majority of the respondents had medium innovativeness, still there is a lot need to expose the farmers to new developments in agriculture technologies and motivate them to adopt the new technologies by organizing group discussions, meetings and field trips.

The study revealed that certain variable such as education, land holding, annual income, credibility, planning orientation, risk orientation, marketing behaviour found significant relationship with entrepreneurial behaviour. The Government and private organizations should aim at manipulating these variables to their advantage for promoting entrepreneurs in floriculture. This results are in line with findings of Bhaskar *et al.* (2019); Mahanta *et al.* (2020); Gaikwad and Lalhriatpuii (2018) and Swati *et al.* 2017. They reported that more than three-fifth (67.50%) of the commercial floriculture nursery owners possessed medium entrepreneurial behavior followed by 16.67 per cent of them with high level of entrepreneurial behaviour and only 15.83 per cent of them with low level of entrepreneurial behavior.

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Rec. on 23.11.2023 & Acc. on 21.12.2023